

Psychological and Cognitive Profiles of Laid-Off Nurses: An Exploratory Cluster Analysis-Based Study

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Abstract

Introduction: This study analyzed the psychological and cognitive profiles of a sample of laid-off nurses, utilizing cluster analysis to identify groups with similar characteristics. The aim was to better understand the impact of job loss on psychological well-being and to develop targeted interventions to support these individuals.

Methods: Data were collected with the MMPI-2 and the Raven's Matrices test, from 45 laid-off nurses. Cluster analysis was used to identify distinct groups of individuals with similar characteristics

Results: The analysis revealed two distinct clusters: *Cluster 1 ("Adaptable and Resilient")*: This cluster includes individuals with a high IQ (125), a tendency to present themselves in a favorable light, and general psychological stability, with scores within the normal range for anxiety, depression, and other psychological disorders. *Cluster 2 ("Anxious and Vulnerable")*: This cluster includes individuals with high levels of anxiety, depression, hypochondria, and other psychological difficulties, despite a high IQ (121). These individuals also exhibit greater concerns about health and problems in social and work relationships.

Discussion: The results indicate that job loss has a differential impact on nurses, with some maintaining psychological stability and others developing significant difficulties. Intervention strategies should be personalized: Cluster 1 may benefit from professional development programs and career coaching, while Cluster 2 requires intensive psychotherapeutic interventions to address symptoms of anxiety and depression.

Conclusions: Cluster analysis provides an in-depth understanding of the differences in the psychological profiles of laid-off nurses. These findings can guide the implementation of targeted interventions to improve psychological well-being and facilitate the reintegration of nurses into the workforce, helping to mitigate the negative effects of job loss.

Keywords: Job loss; laid-off nurses; occupational mental health; psychological well-being; MMPI-2; Raven's Progressive Matrices; intelligence quotient; cluster analysis; resilience; work reintegration.

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INTRODUCTION

Job loss is an event that can have significant consequences on individuals' lives, affecting not only their economic well-being but also their mental health and emotional state. This phenomenon takes on particular importance in the healthcare sector, where job loss can have repercussions not only on the nurses themselves but also on the healthcare system and the patients who depend on their care. In this context, it becomes crucial to examine the impact of job loss on nurses, considering how personality traits and IQ, in terms of problem-solving abilities and adaptability, may influence their experiences and reactions to this event.

Job loss is often associated with a range of negative psychological and emotional effects. Losing a job can lead to stress, anxiety, depression, and a decrease in self-esteem. Several studies have shown that job loss can be a significant risk factor for the development of mental disorders. For example, Kessler et al. [1] found that unemployment is associated with an increased risk of major depression and other mood disorders. Similarly, McKee-Ryan et al. [2] highlighted that job loss can severely compromise individuals' psychological well-being, negatively impacting their quality of life.

The economic consequences of job loss are evident and immediate. The loss of income can lead to financial difficulties, indebtedness, and a decrease in the standard of living. However, the repercussions go beyond the economic aspect, also affecting social and family relationships. Laid-off individuals may experience social isolation, a reduction in support networks, and increased tension in personal relationships [3-5].

According to a study by Brand [6], job loss can have long-term effects on social mobility and future career opportunities, reducing prospects for earnings and promotions.

Personality and resilience theories

Personality theories provide a useful framework for understanding how individual traits influence responses to job loss [7]. The Big Five model [8] is particularly relevant as it identifies five fundamental dimensions of personality:

neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness. Each of these traits can influence individuals' resilience in different ways. For example, high levels of conscientiousness are associated with greater self-discipline and perseverance, which can facilitate job searching and adaptation to new work situations [9]. Conversely, high levels of neuroticism can lead to greater vulnerability to stress and negative emotions, hindering the reemployment process.

Bandura [10] emphasized the importance of self-efficacy, or the belief in one's abilities to tackle and overcome challenges, as a crucial factor for resilience. Individuals with high self-efficacy are more likely to view job loss as an opportunity for growth rather than an insurmountable obstacle, adopting a more proactive approach to job searching.

The role of Intelligence Quotient (IQ)

The Intelligence Quotient (IQ) has long been considered an important predictor of professional success [11]. Studies such as those by Schmidt and Hunter [12] have demonstrated that IQ is positively correlated with job performance and learning ability. A high IQ is associated with better problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and adaptability to new work environments—all crucial competencies during the post-layoff transition.

Spearman's theory of cognitive abilities [13] introduces the concept of "g" or general intelligence, which suggests that an underlying common factor contributes to various types of cognitive abilities. This concept is supported by research showing that individuals with high "g" scores tend to succeed in a wide range of professional activities. However, it is important to note that IQ alone is not sufficient to guarantee success; the combination of cognitive and metacognitive abilities, personality traits, and social skills is essential for effective adaptation and success in the workplace [14].

IQ is another important factor that can influence the experiences of laid-off nurses. A high IQ is often associated with better problem-solving abilities, more developed critical thinking, and greater adaptability to new and stressful situations [15]. These attributes can be particularly useful when facing the work transition after a layoff. For example, a study [16] highlighted that individuals with high IQs tend to find more effective and creative solutions to unemployment-related problems.

IQ also has a direct impact on professional success and career opportunities. People with high IQs tend to perform better at work, achieve promotions more quickly, and earn higher salaries [11]. This may mean that even after a layoff, individuals with high IQs are more likely to find new employment relatively quickly and maintain a positive career trajectory [17]. However, it is important to note that IQ alone does not determine success; the combination of intelligence, personality, and social skills plays a crucial role in determining reemployment opportunities [18].

Hypotheses of the present study

In this study, it was hypothesized that cluster analysis could identify distinct groups of laid-off nurses based on their personality traits and IQ. The central hypothesis is that specific clusters exist that significantly differ in their psychological and cognitive characteristics, and that these clusters could provide useful insights into how different groups of individuals react to job loss and what support strategies might be most effective for each group [11,19].

As a hypothesis, it is proposed that cluster analysis could identify distinct personality clusters among laid-off individuals, each with unique psychological and cognitive profiles. One potential cluster might include "Adaptable and Resilient" individuals who are highly organized, emotionally stable, and proactive in job searching due to their high conscientiousness and low neuroticism. Another cluster, "Anxious and Vulnerable," may consist of individuals with high anxiety and emotional instability, who struggle with organization and social interaction, potentially requiring intensive psychological support.

Additionally, a cluster of "Optimistic and Proactive" individuals, characterized by extroversion, openness to experience, and low neuroticism, may emerge, highlighting their effectiveness in job searching and handling new professional challenges. The hypothesis also anticipates a "Isolated and Suspicious" cluster, where individuals may be distrustful, socially isolated, and in need of interventions focused on building trust and social skills.

The "Creative and Restless" cluster is expected to include highly creative but anxious individuals who could benefit from strategies to manage their anxiety. Finally, the "Independent and Competitive" cluster might consist of highly competitive and assertive individuals, who, despite being success-oriented, may require support to improve their relational skills while aggressively seeking new opportunities after job loss.

The basic hypothesis of the present study is that cluster analysis, applied to data collected through the MMPI-2 and the Raven's Matrices test, could reveal different distinct personality groups among laid-off nurses. These clusters could reflect specific combinations of personality traits and cognitive abilities [17,20,21].

METHODS

Procedure

Before collecting any data, participants were provided with detailed information explaining the purposes of the study, the procedures involved, potential risks and benefits, and the measures taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity. Each participant signed an informed consent form, stating that they understood the provided information and voluntarily agreed to participate in the study. The data processing procedure was reviewed and approved by an independent ethics committee before the study began. This committee ensured that all practices complied with ethical and legal standards.

Data collection for the cluster analysis was based on the use of standardized and validated tools to measure the personality traits and IQ of nurses who were laid off between 2022 and 2023. The Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory-2 (MMPI-2) was used to assess a wide range of personality traits, while Raven's Progressive Matrices were used to measure IQ. These tools are widely recognized for their reliability and validity, making them ideal for this type of research.

Instruments

Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory-2 (MMPI-2)

The Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory-2 (MMPI-2) [22] is one of the most widely used and respected psychometric tools for assessing personality and psychopathology. Originally developed in the 1940s and later revised in 1989, the MMPI-2 consists of 567 items (questions) that require true/false responses.

The MMPI-2 is designed to assess a broad range of psychological problems and personality traits. It is used in various clinical and research settings, including the diagnosis of mental disorders, personnel selection, pre-employment evaluation, and forensic contexts. Its applications include assessing mood disorders, anxiety, schizophrenia, and other psychological disorders.

The MMPI-2 contains several clinical scales, validity scales, and content scales.

Clinical Scales. The primary clinical scales include: Hypochondriasis (Hs): Measures somatic concerns; Depression (D): Assesses depressive symptoms.; Hysteria (Hy): Measures psychophysiological reactions to stress; Psychopathic Deviation (Pd): Evaluates antisocial behaviors; Masculinity-Femininity (Mf): Measures gender roles and interests; Paranoia (Pa): Assesses paranoid symptoms and ideas of reference; Psychasthenia (Pt): Measures anxiety and obsessive tendencies; Schizophrenia (Sc): Evaluates disorganized thoughts and behaviors; Hypomania (Ma): Measures excessive energy and restlessness.; Social Introversion (Si): Assesses introverted tendencies and social isolation.

Validity Scales. The validity scales are used to assess the sincerity and consistency of the subject's responses, helping to identify any attempts to present themselves in an overly positive or negative light. The main validity scales include: L (Lie): Measures the subject's inclination to present themselves in an overly positive manner; F (Frequency): Identifies atypical or exaggerated responses; K (Correction): Evaluates defensiveness and the tendency to minimize problems.

Content Scales. The content scales are designed to assess specific areas of concern and behavior. These scales offer a more detailed view of the subject's specific issues. The main content scales include: Anxiety (ANX): Measures levels of anxiety *and* tension; Fears (FRS): Assesses specific fears and phobias; Obsessiveness (OBS): Measures obsessive thoughts and behaviors; Depression (DEP): Assesses specific depressive symptoms; Health Concerns (HEA): Measures health-related concerns and symptoms; Anger (ANG): Evaluates feelings of anger and hostility; Antisocial Practices (ASP): Measures antisocial behaviors and attitudes; Low Self-Esteem (LSE): Assesses the subject's sense of self-esteem; Family Problems (FAM): Measures family problems and conflicts; Marital Distress (MAR): Assesses relational and marital issues; Work Interference (WRK): Measures difficulties and dissatisfaction related to work; Negative Treatment Indicators (TRT): Assesses potential difficulties with therapeutic compliance.

These content scales help provide a more comprehensive picture of the subject's psychological issues, enabling more accurate diagnosis and more effective treatment planning.

Raven's Progressive Matrices

The Raven's Progressive Matrices [23], officially known as Raven's Progressive Matrices, is a non-verbal test used to measure fluid intelligence and problem-solving abilities. Developed by John C. Raven in 1936, it is widely used to assess intelligence quotient (IQ). The test is designed to evaluate a person's ability to form perceptions, analyze, and think abstractly, without the influence of language and culture. It is often used in educational, corporate, and clinical settings to assess the cognitive abilities of individuals of different ages and backgrounds.

The Raven's Progressive Matrices test consists of a series of visual matrices, each of which presents an incomplete pattern that must be completed by selecting the missing part from several options. There are different versions of the test: a) Standard Progressive Matrices (SPM): The original version, suitable for most general assessments. b) Coloured Progressive Matrices (CPM): Used for young children, the elderly, or individuals with cognitive disabilities. c) Advanced Progressive Matrices (APM): Intended for individuals with higher intellectual abilities, such as university students or candidates for managerial positions.

The test consists of 60 questions divided into 5 sets of increasing difficulty. The items are designed to assess a person's ability to identify logical relationships between shapes and patterns. Performance on the test is usually expressed as a standardized IQ score, which can be compared to group norms to determine the subject's relative intelligence level. In this study, the Standard Progressive Matrices (SPM) were used.

Sample

The sample analyzed in this study consists of 45 nurses from Southern Italy (15 males and 30 females) aged between 34 and 59 years ($M=44.93$; $SD=5.98$). These individuals were recruited during medical evaluations for work fitness. These medical evaluations were conducted to assess the professionals' ability to performing their roles, often in response to health issues or other circumstances that might affect their fitness for work.

The participants in the sample were selected from those who had been laid off due to budget cuts, not because of deficits in their work performance or behavior. This targeted selection provides a unique population to study the psychological and cognitive impact of job loss, considering that the triggering factors were not related to personal performance but to external circumstances.

Data analysis

Cluster analysis was performed using SPSS 27.0 software, employing the K-means algorithm, an unsupervised clustering technique that groups data based on similarity. Before applying the algorithm, the scores of the variables of interest (personality traits and IQ) were standardized to ensure that each variable contributed equally to the formation of the clusters (Table 1). The optimal number of clusters was determined using the elbow method and silhouette score, which help identify the number of clusters that best represent the data structure.

The K-means algorithm was executed iteratively, starting with the random selection of k centroids, and subsequently assigning each data point to the nearest centroid. After the assignment, the centroids were recalculated as the mean of the data points assigned to each cluster. This process was repeated until the cluster assignments stabilized, minimizing within-cluster variance and maximizing between-cluster variance.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of age, intelligence quotient, and MMPI-2 scale scores.

Variable	Mean	SD	Skewness (SE)	Kurtosis (SE)	Min	Max
Age, years	44.93	5.98	0.11 (0.35)	-0.37 (0.70)	34	59
Raven IQ	124.16	6.36	-2.10 (0.35)	3.17 (0.70)	105	128
L – Lie	56.09	10.92	0.62 (0.35)	0.19 (0.70)	39	85
F – Frequency	45.38	5.79	2.26 (0.35)	8.10 (0.70)	37	71
K – Correction	50.67	8.38	-0.31 (0.35)	-0.82 (0.70)	32	64
Hs – Hypochondriasis	51.89	7.19	0.35 (0.35)	-0.30 (0.70)	38	68
D – Depression	48.22	8.36	0.54 (0.35)	1.03 (0.70)	32	72
Hy – Hysteria	47.07	7.94	0.83 (0.35)	1.23 (0.70)	31	72
Pd – Psychopathic Deviation	50.36	6.51	0.41 (0.35)	2.34 (0.70)	37	73
Mf – Masculinity/Femininity	49.11	8.76	0.15 (0.35)	-0.02 (0.70)	33	72
Pa – Paranoia	44.71	7.66	0.60 (0.35)	0.49 (0.70)	31	68
Pt – Psychasthenia	42.00	7.18	1.11 (0.35)	2.67 (0.70)	30	68
Sc – Schizophrenia	46.33	7.47	0.45 (0.35)	2.09 (0.70)	31	72
Ma – Hypomania	48.40	8.51	0.56 (0.35)	-0.30 (0.70)	32	68
Si – Social Introversion	48.22	8.35	0.79 (0.35)	0.59 (0.70)	34	71
ANX – Anxiety	47.62	6.68	0.46 (0.35)	0.64 (0.70)	34	66
FRS – Fears	50.73	7.46	0.29 (0.35)	0.14 (0.70)	36	71
OBS – Obsessiveness	46.09	7.10	1.04 (0.35)	2.07 (0.70)	33	69
DEP – Depression	46.02	5.71	0.59 (0.35)	0.85 (0.70)	35	63
HEA – Health Concerns	49.60	6.81	0.45 (0.35)	-0.18 (0.70)	37	66
BIZ – Bizarre Ideation	48.18	7.99	0.26 (0.35)	-1.03 (0.70)	38	66
ANG – Anger	45.84	7.59	0.20 (0.35)	-0.81 (0.70)	33	59
CYN – Cynicism	54.00	8.98	0.34 (0.35)	-1.07 (0.70)	39	70
ASP – Antisocial Behavior	48.47	5.98	0.65 (0.35)	0.41 (0.70)	39	64

TPA – Type A	46.84	6.77	0.61 (0.35)	-0.05 (0.70)	35	65
LSE – Low Self-Esteem	46.22	7.54	0.46 (0.35)	-0.17 (0.70)	32	65
SOD – Social Discomfort	47.91	7.76	0.87 (0.35)	1.09 (0.70)	37	73
FAM – Family Problems	45.80	8.01	1.53 (0.35)	3.32 (0.70)	35	74
WRK – Work Difficulties	44.96	7.08	0.91 (0.35)	1.74 (0.70)	34	69
TRT – Treatment Difficulties	48.02	7.32	0.20 (0.35)	0.23 (0.70)	34	65

Note: Values are reported as mean, standard deviation (SD), skewness, kurtosis, minimum and maximum. MMPI-2 scale scores are expressed as T-scores. Age is expressed in years, while Raven scores are reported as intelligence quotient (IQ) values. SE: standard error; IQ: intelligence quotient; MMPI-2: Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory-2.

RESULTS

The resulting clusters were analyzed to identify the distinctive characteristics of each group (Table 2). Differences in personality traits and IQ scores among the clusters were examined (Table 3), and the practical implications of these differences were explored.

Table 2. Initial and final cluster centers from K-means cluster analysis.

Variable	Initial Cluster 1	Initial Cluster 2	Final Cluster 1 (n=40)	Final Cluster 2 (n=5)
Raven IQ	128	120	125	121
L – Lie	81	58	56	53
F – Infrequency	42	71	44	54
K – Correction	57	44	52	40
Hs – Hypochondriasis	47	63	51	60
D – Depression	39	72	47	60
Hy – Hysteria	42	52	46	55
Pd – Psychopathic Deviation	46	73	50	53
Mf – Masculinity/Femininity	65	48	49	48
Pa – Paranoia	36	68	44	54
Pt – Psychasthenia	34	68	41	51
Sc – Schizophrenia	50	72	46	52
Ma – Hypomania	50	66	47	60
Si – Social Introversion	41	71	47	61
ANX – Anxiety	34	54	47	56
FRS – Fears	36	57	50	55
OBS – Obsessiveness	37	61	45	58
DEP – Depression	39	63	45	54
HEA – Health Concerns	42	54	49	57

BIZ – Bizarre Ideation	38	63	47	59
ANG – Anger	37	58	45	54
CYN – Cynicism	51	67	53	60
ASP – Antisocial Behavior	50	50	48	55
TPA – Type A	35	56	46	50
LSE – Low Self-Esteem	36	65	45	58
SOD – Social Discomfort	43	73	46	60
FAM – Family Problems	35	74	44	59
WRK – Work Difficulties	35	69	43	58
TRT – Treatment Difficulties	43	58	47	60

Note: Values represent cluster centers obtained through K-means cluster analysis. MMPI-2 scale scores are expressed as T-scores, whereas Raven scores are reported as intelligence quotient (IQ) values. Cluster 1 was interpreted as the “Adaptable and Resilient” profile, while Cluster 2 was interpreted as the “Anxious and Vulnerable” profile. MMPI-2: Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory-2; IQ: intelligence quotient.

Given that the sample consists of laid-off nurses, it is crucial to interpret the results of the cluster analysis in the context of the additional stress and psychological implications of job loss. Below is an in-depth description of the profiles of the two identified clusters, taking into account the context of job loss.

Cluster 1: More Psychologically Stable Profile (“Adaptable and Resilient”)

Individuals in Cluster 1 (N=40) exhibit a very high level of intelligence, with an IQ of 125. This suggests that they may possess superior cognitive abilities that help them better adapt to stressful situations such as job loss. The L (Lie) score of 56 indicates a moderately high tendency to present themselves in a favorable light, possibly to maintain a positive image even during stressful periods. The F (Frequency) score of 44, which is below the norm, indicates a lower frequency of atypical responses, reflecting psychological stability despite the job loss. The K (Correction) score of 52 suggests a moderate tendency towards defensiveness, indicating that these individuals can manage stress in a balanced way. Scores for Hs (Hypochondriasis) at 51, D (Depression) at 47, Hy (Hysteria) at 46, Pd (Psychopathic Deviation) at 50, and Pt (Psychasthenia) at 41 are all within the normal range, suggesting typical levels of health concerns, depression, hysterical symptoms, psychopathic deviation, and anxiety, respectively.

The Sc (Schizophrenia) score of 46 indicates low levels of positive symptoms, reflecting general mental stability. The Ma (Hypomania) score of 47 suggests low levels of manic symptoms, indicating stable emotional control. The SI (Social Introversion) score of 47 shows typical levels of social introversion, indicating that job loss has not significantly altered social interactions. The ANX (Anxiety) score of 47 reflects low levels of anxiety, suggesting good stress management related to the job loss. Finally, the CYN (Cynicism) score of 53, slightly above the norm, suggests a tendency towards cynicism, possibly as a defense mechanism.

In summary, Cluster 1 includes individuals who, despite the job loss, maintain overall psychological stability and demonstrate resilience. They are able to manage stress and emotions effectively, likely due to high cognitive abilities and functional coping strategies.

Cluster 2: Profile with Significant Difficulties (“Anxious and Vulnerable”)

Individuals in Cluster 2 (N=5) also exhibit a high level of intelligence, with an IQ of 121, although on average lower than Cluster 1. This still suggests good cognitive abilities. The L (Lie) score of 53 indicates a lower tendency to present themselves in a favorable light, possibly due to greater psychological stress. The F (Frequency) score of 54, above the

norm, indicates a higher number of unusual responses, reflecting psychological instability due to the job loss. The K (Correction) score of 40 suggests lower defensiveness, indicating emotional vulnerability and difficulty managing stress. Scores for Hs (Hypochondriasis) at 60, D (Depression) at 60, Hy (Hysteria) at 55, Pd (Psychopathic Deviation) at 53, and Pt (Psychasthenia) at 51 indicate elevated levels of health concerns, depression, and other psychological difficulties, suggesting a strong negative response to the job loss. The Sc (Schizophrenia) score of 52 indicates distress levels within the norm. The Ma (Hypomania) score around 60 suggests elevated levels of manic symptoms, indicating unstable emotional responses. The SI (Social Introversion) score of 61 indicates higher social introversion, suggesting isolation and difficulties in social interactions. The ANX (Anxiety) score of 56 reflects elevated levels of anxiety, suggesting a strong anxious response to the job loss. Finally, the CYN (Cynicism) score of 60 indicates high levels of cynicism, suggesting a negative and defensive worldview.

In summary, Cluster 2 includes individuals who exhibit significant psychological instability and emotional difficulties in response to the job loss. These individuals display elevated levels of depression, hypochondria, and other psychological challenges, which may be exacerbated by the loss of employment.

Table 3. Differences between clusters across Raven IQ and MMPI-2 scales.

Variable	Cluster MS	Error MS	F(1,43)	p-value
Raven IQ	42.71	40.40	1.06	0.310
L – Lie	53.67	120.70	0.45	0.508
F – Infrequency	418.18	24.61	16.99	<0.001
K – Correction	640.00	57.02	11.22	0.002
Hs – Hypochondriasis	334.47	45.07	7.42	0.009
D – Depression	728.18	54.60	13.34	0.001
Hy – Hysteria	336.40	56.71	5.93	0.019
Pd – Psychopathic Deviation	39.34	42.49	0.93	0.341
Mf – Masculinity/Femininity	6.94	78.36	0.09	0.767
Pa – Paranoia	528.04	47.80	11.05	0.002
Pt – Psychasthenia	435.60	42.57	10.23	0.003
Sc – Schizophrenia	193.60	52.61	3.68	0.062
Ma – Hypomania	810.00	55.18	14.68	<0.001
Si – Social Introversion	947.38	49.27	19.23	<0.001
ANX – Anxiety	413.88	35.97	11.51	0.001
FRS – Fears	84.10	54.95	1.53	0.223
OBS – Obsessiveness	852.54	31.79	26.82	<0.001
DEP – Depression	323.00	25.81	12.51	0.001
HEA – Health Concerns	324.90	39.95	8.13	0.007
BIZ – Bizarre Ideation	658.80	49.95	13.19	0.001
ANG – Anger	338.34	51.06	6.63	0.014

CYN – Cynicism	189.23	78.02	2.43	0.127
ASP – Antisocial Behavior	240.10	31.05	7.73	0.008
TPA – Type A	71.11	45.18	1.57	0.216
LSE – Low Self-Esteem	728.18	41.29	17.63	<0.001
SOD – Social Discomfort	877.34	41.22	21.29	<0.001
FAM – Family Problems	921.60	44.22	20.84	<0.001
WRK – Work Difficulties	957.14	29.04	32.96	<0.001
TRT – Treatment Difficulties	807.00	36.09	22.36	<0.001

Note: Values are derived from the ANOVA output comparing the two clusters identified through K-means cluster analysis. Statistically significant p-values are shown in bold. Since the clusters were generated from the same variables included in the analysis, these ANOVA results should be interpreted as descriptive indicators of the variables contributing to cluster differentiation rather than as independent confirmatory hypothesis tests. MS: mean square; IQ: intelligence quotient; MMPI-2: Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory-2.

DISCUSSION

This study contributes to the existing literature exploring the impact of job loss on mental health and the role of personality and IQ in moderating these outcomes [17, 24]. The cluster analysis identified two distinct profiles among the laid-off nurses, with significant differences in psychological and cognitive characteristics. Understanding these profiles is crucial for developing targeted interventions that can support the psychological and professional well-being of individuals affected by job loss [21,25,26].

Individuals in Cluster 1 exhibit a high level of intelligence (IQ = 125), tend to present themselves in a socially desirable manner, and show general psychological stability, with scores within the normal range for anxiety, depression, and other psychological disorders. These findings align with previous studies suggesting that intelligence can serve as a protective factor against the stress and anxiety associated with job loss [15,17,27,28]. The tendency to present themselves favorably (L - Lie = 56) might reflect a coping strategy that helps maintain a positive self-image during stressful periods. Literature indicates that people with high levels of social desirability tend to manage stress better through social support and maintaining positive relationships [29-31].

Cluster 2 presents a significantly different profile, characterized by elevated levels of anxiety, depression, hypochondria, and other psychological difficulties. These individuals have a high IQ (IQ = 121) but lower on average compared to Cluster 1 and show a lower tendency to present themselves favorably (L - Lie = 53). The presence of elevated symptoms of anxiety (ANX = 56), depression (D = 60), and hypochondria (Hs = 60) suggests that the job loss has had a marked negative impact on their psychological well-being.

These results are consistent with literature highlighting how job loss can exacerbate pre-existing mental health issues, leading to higher levels of psychological distress and depressive symptoms [6, 32-36]. Additionally, the higher social introversion (SI = 61) and social discomfort (SOD = 60) may indicate that these individuals struggle to seek and receive social support, further increasing their risk of developing mental health problems [37-41].

From a cognitive-behavioral perspective, we can better understand how thoughts and emotions influence our reactions to events such as job loss. This theory posits that thoughts (cognitions) influence emotions and, consequently, behaviors. In other words, how we interpret an adverse event can determine our emotional and behavioral response [42,43].

Individuals in Cluster 1 seem to possess thoughts and beliefs that help them interpret job loss as less threatening, thereby maintaining psychological stability. Their high intelligence and functional coping strategies may contribute to generating more rational and less catastrophic thoughts, allowing them to better cope with stress.

On the other hand, individuals in Cluster 2 exhibit more negative thoughts and beliefs regarding job loss, leading to greater psychological instability and emotional difficulties. Their lower tendency to present themselves favorably might reflect a greater awareness and honesty about their emotional state but also a predisposition to interpret events more pessimistically [44,45].

Understanding these individual differences is crucial, as not everyone responds negatively to adverse events [46, 47]. Some may see job loss as an opportunity for growth and development, while others may perceive it as a catastrophe. Targeted interventions that account for these differences can be more effective in supporting individuals affected by job loss, promoting more adaptive thoughts and effective coping strategies to improve their psychological well-being [48-53].

Some implications for clinical practice can indeed be discussed. In light of the results, interventions for Cluster 1 should focus on maintaining their psychological stability and developing professional skills. Career coaching and professional retraining programs could be particularly effective.

Individuals in Cluster 2 might benefit from intensive psychotherapeutic interventions to address symptoms of anxiety, depression, and other psychological difficulties. Therapies such as cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) and family therapy could be useful in improving psychological well-being and social relationships [54, 55].

Limitations

It is important to recognize some limitations of the study. The sample size could influence the generalizability of the results. Additionally, the data were collected in a specific context (laid-off nurses) and may not be representative of other populations. Future studies could benefit from larger samples and greater professional diversity to further validate these findings.

CONCLUSIONS

The cluster analysis highlighted two distinct profiles among the laid-off nurses, with significant differences in psychological and cognitive characteristics. These results underscore the importance of personalized interventions to address the diverse psychological needs of individuals affected by job loss. Understanding the differences in psychological profiles can inform the development of targeted support strategies to improve psychological well-being and facilitate reintegration into the workforce.

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References

1. Kessler RC, Turner JB, House JS. Unemployment, reemployment, and emotional functioning in a community sample. *Am Sociol Rev.* 1987;52(4):649-659. doi:10.2307/2095606.
2. McKee-Ryan FM, Song Z, Wanberg CR, et al. Psychological and physical well-being during unemployment: A meta-analytic study. *J Appl Psychol.* 2005;90(1):53-76. doi:10.1037/0021-9010.90.1.53.
3. Rizzo A, Yıldırım M, Öztekin GG, et al. Nurse burnout before and during the COVID-19 pandemic: a systematic comparative review. *Front Public Health.* 2023 Sep 5;11:1225431.
4. Rizzo A, Yıldırım M, Aziz IA, et al. Anxiety and Coping Strategies among Italian-Speaking Physicians: A Comparative Analysis of the Contractually Obligated and Voluntary Care of COVID-19 Patients. *InHealthcare* 2023 Nov 26;11(23), p. 3044.
5. Rizzo A, Alfa R, Carlotta V, et al. Burnout, decision-making and coping among healthcare workers: how the world was before the COVID-19 pandemic. *G Ital Psicol Med Lav.* 2022;2(2):105-116.
6. Brand JE. The far-reaching impact of job loss and unemployment. *Annu Rev Sociol.* 2015;41:359-375. doi:10.1146/annurev-soc-071913-043237.
7. Costa PT, McCrae RR. Four ways five factors are basic. *Pers Individ Dif.* 1992;13(6):653-665. doi:10.1016/0191-8869(92)90236-I.
8. Goldberg LR. The development of markers for the Big-Five factor structure. *Psychol Assess.* 1992;4(1):26-42. doi:10.1037/1040-3590.4.1.26.
9. Rizzo A, Marra P. Temperament, Character and Organisational well-being among Obstetrics and Gynaecology Personnel: a pilot study. *Quad Psicol.* 2023;25(3):9.
10. Bandura A. *Self-Efficacy: The Exercise of Control.* New York: Freeman; 1997.
11. Strenze T. Intelligence and socioeconomic success: A meta-analytic review of longitudinal research. *Intelligence.* 2007;35(5):401-426. doi: 10.1016/j.intell.2006.09.004.
12. Schmidt FL, Hunter JE. General mental ability in the world of work: Occupational attainment and job performance. *J Pers Soc Psychol.* 2004;86(1):162-173. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.86.1.162.
13. Spearman C. "General Intelligence," Objectively Determined and Measured. *Am J Psychol.* 1904;15(2):201-292. doi:10.2307/1412107.
14. Ait Ben Ali S, Korchyoun Y, Ait Baja Z, et al. Metacognitive learning strategies and academic performance: A correlational study among Moroccan nursing students. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health.* 2024;1(3):125-132. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10901038.
15. Kaufman SB. *Ungifted: Intelligence Redefined.* Basic Books; 2013.
16. Gottfredson LS. Intelligence: Is it the epidemiologists' elusive "fundamental cause" of social class inequalities in health? *J Pers Soc Psychol.* 2004;86(1):174-199. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.86.1.174.
17. Deary IJ, Weiss A, Batty GD. Intelligence and personality as predictors of illness and death: How researchers are discovering the link between physical health and intelligence. *Am Sci.* 2010;98(4):360-368. doi:10.1511/2010.85.1211.
18. Arthur MB, Khapova SN, Wilderom CPM. Career success in a boundaryless career world. *J Organ Behav.* 2005;26(2):177-202. doi:10.1002/job.290.
19. McCrae RR, Costa PT Jr. *Personality in Adulthood: A Five-Factor Theory Perspective.* 2nd ed. New York: Guilford Press; 2003.
20. Judge TA, Bono JE, Thoresen CJ, et al. The job satisfaction–job performance relationship: A qualitative and quantitative review. *Psychol Bull.* 2001;127(3):376-407. doi:10.1037/0033-2909.127.3.376.
21. Salgado JF, Táuriz G. The five factor model, forced-choice personality inventories and performance: A comprehensive meta-analysis

- of academic and occupational validity studies. *Eur J Work Organ Psychol.* 2014;23(1):3-30. doi:10.1080/1359432X.2012.716198.
22. Butcher JN, Dahlstrom WG, Graham JR, et al. Manual for administration and scoring. Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory—2: MMPI-2. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press; 1989.
 23. Raven JC 1936. Mental tests used in genetic studies: The performance of related individuals on tests mainly educative and mainly reproductive. University of London; 1936.
 24. John OP, Srivastava S. The Big Five trait taxonomy: History, measurement, and theoretical perspectives. In: Pervin LA, John OP, eds. *Handbook of Personality: Theory and Research*. 2nd ed. New York: Guilford Press; 1999:102-138.
 25. Peiró JM, Kozusznik MW, Rodríguez-Molina I, et al. The happy-productive worker model and beyond: Patterns of wellbeing and performance at work. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2019;16(3):479. doi:10.3390/ijerph16030479.
 26. Rizzo A. Professional identity and personal value in occupational health psychology: Overlap or eclipse? *G Ital Psicol Med Lav.* 2023;3(1):17-20.
 27. Judge TA, Higgins CA, Thoresen CJ, et al. The Big Five personality traits, general mental ability, and career success across the life span. *Pers Psychol.* 2009;52(3):621-652.
 28. Hart CL, Smith GD, Whitley E, et al. Impact of educational attainment on the association between IQ and mortality: prospective cohort study. *BMJ.* 2006;332(7541):580-584.
 29. Paulhus DL, Reid DB. Enhancement and denial in socially desirable responding. *J Pers Soc Psychol.* 1991;60(2):307-317.
 30. Lucas RE, Diener E, Suh E. Discriminant validity of well-being measures. *J Pers Soc Psychol.* 1996;71(3):616-628. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.71.3.616.
 31. Fredrickson BL. The broaden-and-build theory of positive emotions. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci.* 2004;359(1449):1367-1378. doi:10.1098/rstb.2004.1512.
 32. Dooley D, Prause J, Ham-Rowbottom KA. Underemployment and depression: Longitudinal relationships. *J Health Soc Behav.* 2000;41(4):421-436.
 33. Dooley D, Fielding J, Levi L. Health and unemployment. *Annu Rev Public Health.* 1996;17:449-465. doi: 10.1146/annurev.pu.17.050196.002313.
 34. Cacioppo JT, Hawkley LC, Thisted RA. Perceived social isolation makes me sad: Five year cross-lagged analyses of loneliness and depressive symptomatology in the Chicago Health, Aging, and Social Relations Study. *Psychol Aging.* 2006;21(1):140-151.
 35. Cooper CL, Dewe PJ, O'Driscoll MP. *Organizational Stress: A Review and Critique of Theory, Research, and Applications*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications; 2001.
 36. Hough LM, Furnham A. Use of personality variables in work settings. In: Hogan R, Johnson J, Briggs S, eds. *Handbook of Personality Psychology*. San Diego: Academic Press; 1997:1017-1043.
 37. Ait Ali D, Ncila O, Ouhamou S, et al. Motivations Driving Career Choices: Insights From a Study Among Nursing Students. *SAGE Open Nursing.* 2024 May;10:23779608241255876.
 38. Qourrichi A, Ouazizi K, Saaliti E, et al. The effect of learned helplessness on the psychological health of healthcare workers. *J Health Soc Sci.* 2024;9(1):129-143.
 39. Chirico F. Navigating in the global workplace: Innovative strategies for combating new approach to preventing burnout, violence, preventing and workplace enhancing psychosocial well-being. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health.* 2024;1(3):108-109. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10897920.
 40. Eysenck HJ. *The Structure of Human Personality*. London: Methuen; 1953.
 41. Mischel W. *Personality and Assessment*. New York: Wiley; 1968.
 42. Lazarus RS, Folkman S. *Stress, Appraisal, and Coping*. New York: Springer Publishing Company; 1984.
 43. Carver CS, Scheier MF. *On the Self-Regulation of Behavior*. New York: Cambridge University Press; 1998.

44. Baumeister RF, Vohs KD. *Handbook of Self-Regulation: Research, Theory, and Applications*. New York: Guilford Press; 2004.
45. Hobfoll SE. *The Ecology of Stress*. New York: Hemisphere Publishing Corporation; 1988.
46. Chirico F, Rizzo A. Tackling mental health disorders, burnout, workplace violence, post-traumatic stress disorders amidst climate change, and new global challenges: The crucial role of emotional management education. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2024;2(1):5-7.
47. Makkaoui M, Hannoun Fz, Ouazizi K, et al. Spirituality as predictor of psychological well-being at work in the Moroccan context: A cross-sectional study. *J Health Soc Sci*. 2024;9(2):279-293.
48. Tarchi L, Crescenzo P, Castellini G, et al. Volunteer-aholism: A comprehensive model of personality, burnout, and mental distress in a sample of healthcare first responders of the Italian Red Cross Auxiliary Corps. *J Health Soc Sci*. 2023;8(2):103-120.
49. Yildirim M, Turan ME, Albeladi NS, et al. Resilience and perceived social support as predictors of emotional well-being. *J Health Soc Sci*. 2023;8(1):59-75.
50. Rizzo A, Yildirim M, Maggio MG, et al. Novel measures to assess work-life balance: A systematic review of last 5 years (2018-2023). *J Health Soc Sci*. 2023;3:0174-5912.
51. Fugate M, Kinicki AJ, Ashforth BE. Employability: A psycho-social construct, its dimensions, and applications. *J Vocat Behav*. 2004;65(1):14-38.
52. Bateman TS, Crant JM. The proactive component of organizational behavior: A measure and correlates. *J Organ Behav*. 1993;14(2):103-118. doi:10.1002/job.4030140202.
53. Folkman S, Moskowitz JT. Positive affect and the other side of coping. *Am Psychol*. 2000;55(6):647-654. doi:10.1037/0003-066X.55.6.647.
54. Hofmann SG, Asnaani A, Vonk IJ, et al. The efficacy of cognitive behavioral therapy: A review of meta-analyses. *Cognit Ther Res*. 2012;36(5):427-440.
55. Khabbache H, Ait Ali D. Neuroplasticity and cognitive development: Interdisciplinary perspectives on psychotherapeutic and educational approaches. *Adv Med Psych Public Health*. 2025;2(1):1-4. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11234610.

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